

COMBINATORIAL INSIGHTS INTO LEONARDO p -NUMBERS AND LUCAS-LEONARDO p -NUMBERS

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a combinatorial interpretation of Leonardo p -numbers in terms of colored linear tilings and provide combinatorial proofs for several identities involving them. We further explore the incomplete and hyper Leonardo p -numbers, presenting their combinatorial interpretations. Additionally, we present a combinatorial interpretation of the Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers, closely related to Leonardo p -numbers, in terms of colored circular tilings and investigate their combinatorial properties. Finally, we introduce hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers and establish connections with their incomplete counterparts.

1. Introduction

The Fibonacci sequence is among the most well-known sequences in mathematics. The n th Fibonacci number, denoted as F_n , is defined by the recurrence relation $F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}$, $n \geq 2$, with initial values $F_0 = 0$ and $F_1 = 1$. Fibonacci numbers and their extensions exhibit numerous fascinating properties and find diverse applications across science and art. For more details, see [9].

Many authors have explored non-homogeneous extensions of the Fibonacci recurrence relation. In particular, the Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_n\}$, which was used by Dijkstra [8] as an integral part of his sorting algorithm, is defined by the non-homogeneous recurrence relation

$$\mathcal{L}_n = \mathcal{L}_{n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{n-2} + 1, \quad n \geq 2,$$

with initial values $\mathcal{L}_0 = \mathcal{L}_1 = 1$. For the history of Leonardo sequences, see [A001595] in [10]. The properties of the Leonardo numbers have been explored

by Catarino and Borges [6], Alp and Kocer [1], and Shannon [12]. For a fixed positive integer k , Kuhapatanakul and Chobsorn [11] introduced the generalized Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}$ through the non-homogeneous recurrence relation

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,n} = \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{k,n-2} + k, \quad n \geq 2$$

with initial values $\mathcal{L}_{k,0} = \mathcal{L}_{k,1} = 1$. It is clear to see that when $k = 1$, it reduces to the classical Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_n\}$. Additionally, Shattuck [13] provided combinatorial proofs of several identities satisfied by the generalized Leonardo numbers. He also explored some combinatorial aspects of incomplete generalized Leonardo numbers discussed in [7]. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that Bicknell [4] examined a similar type of sequence with arbitrary initial values.

Motivated by the aforementioned studies, Tan and Leung [16] defined a generalization of Leonardo numbers, namely the Leonardo p -numbers. For any given integer $p > 0$, the Leonardo p -numbers are defined by the non-homogeneous relation

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1} + p, \quad n > p, \tag{1}$$

with initial values $\mathcal{L}_{p,0} = \mathcal{L}_{p,1} = \dots = \mathcal{L}_{p,p} = 1$. It is clear to see that when $p = 1$, the Leonardo p -sequence reduces to the classical Leonardo sequence. For the purposes of our paper, we require the following equations (2)-(4) related to the Leonardo p -numbers, which can be found in [16]. The non-homogeneous relation of the Leonardo p -sequence can be converted to the homogeneous relation

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p} - \mathcal{L}_{p,n-2p-1}, \quad n > 2p. \tag{2}$$

A relation between Leonardo p -numbers and Fibonacci p -numbers is given by

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = (p + 1)F_{p,n+1} - p, \tag{3}$$

where $\{F_{p,n}\}$ is the Fibonacci p -sequence defined by the recurrence relation $F_{p,n} = F_{p,n-1} + F_{p,n-p-1}$, $n > p$, with initial values $F_{p,0} = 0$, $F_{p,i} = 1$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$. Note that when $p = 1$, the Fibonacci p -sequence reduces to the classical Fibonacci sequence. For details on Fibonacci p -sequences and their generalizations, we refer to [15]. The incomplete Leonardo p -numbers $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k)$ are defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k) = (p + 1) \sum_{i=0}^k \binom{n-pi}{i} - p, \quad 0 \leq k \leq \left\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \right\rfloor. \tag{4}$$

It is clear to see that $\mathcal{L}_{p,n} \left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \right\rfloor \right) = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}$.

On the other hand, Zhong et al.[17] recently studied a companion sequence of the Leonardo p -sequence, called the Lucas-Leonardo p -sequence, and defined it using the non-homogeneous recurrence relation

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n} = \mathcal{R}_{p,n-1} + \mathcal{R}_{p,n-p-1} + p, \quad n > p \tag{5}$$

with initial values $\mathcal{R}_{p,0} = p^2 + p + 1, \mathcal{R}_{p,1} = \dots = \mathcal{R}_{p,p} = 1$. For $p = 1$, it reduces to the Lucas-Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{R}_n\}$; see [A022319] in [10]. In a similar manner to the Leonardo p -numbers, we require the following equations (6)-(10) for the Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers, which can be found in [17].

A relation between Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers and Lucas p -numbers is given by

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n} = (p + 1) L_{p,n} - p, \tag{6}$$

where $\{L_{p,n}\}$ is the Lucas p -sequence defined by the recurrence relation $L_{p,n} = L_{p,n-1} + L_{p,n-p-1}, n > p$, with initial values $L_{p,0} = p + 1, L_{p,i} = 1$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$. It is clear to see that when $p = 1$, the Lucas p -sequence reduces to the classical Lucas sequence $\{L_n\}$. For details on Lucas p -numbers and their generalizations, see [15]. A relationship between Leonardo p -numbers and Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers is given by

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n} = (p + 1) \mathcal{L}_{p,n} - p\mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}. \tag{7}$$

The incomplete Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers [17] are defined as

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n}(k) = (p + 1) \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{n}{n - pi} \binom{n - pi}{i} - p, \tag{8}$$

where $0 \leq k \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor$. For $0 \leq k \leq \lfloor \frac{n-p-1}{p+1} \rfloor$, the following relation is satisfied:

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n}(k + 1) = \mathcal{R}_{p,n-1}(k + 1) + \mathcal{R}_{p,n-p-1}(k) + p. \tag{9}$$

A relationship between incomplete Leonardo p -numbers and incomplete Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers is

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n}(k) = (p + 1) \mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k) - p\mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}(k). \tag{10}$$

This paper offers a combinatorial perspective on Leonardo p -numbers, illustrating them through colored linear tilings. We provide combinatorial demonstrations of several identities associated with Leonardo p -numbers and incomplete Leonardo p -numbers. In particular, we provide combinatorial proofs of the identities (2)-(4) and more identities given in [16, Proposition 2-5]. Moreover, we establish a connection between incomplete Leonardo p -numbers and hyper Leonardo p -numbers. Similarly, we give a combinatorial interpretation of Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers and provide combinatorial proofs of the identities (6)-(10). We also introduce the concept of hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers and give a relation between incomplete Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers and hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers. Our findings provide combinatorial interpretations and present several novel identities associated with hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers.

2. Combinatorial Interpretation of Leonardo p -numbers

Recall that a (linear) n -board is a board of length n with cells labeled $1, 2, \dots, n$ from left to right. A (linear) n -tiling is a tiling of a (linear) n -board. Suppose that the board is covered by squares and p -minos, where a square covers a single cell and a p -mino covers $p + 1$ cells. Here, a square or a p -mino is indistinguishable from other pieces of the same kind and is denoted by \mathbf{s} or \mathbf{p} , respectively.

Let $f_{p,n}$ denote the set of linear n -tilings consisting of squares and p -minos. Considering whether the last piece within an n -tiling is \mathbf{s} or \mathbf{p} implies

$$|f_{p,n}| = F_{p,n+1}$$

for $n \geq 0$. Note that a member of $f_{p,n}$ containing exactly i p -minos must contain $n - (p + 1)i$ squares, and hence there are $\binom{n-pi}{i}$ such members of $f_{p,n}$ for $0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor$. See [14] for more on the combinatorial interpretation of Fibonacci p -numbers. Also, note that for $p = 1$, it reduces to the combinatorial interpretation of classical Fibonacci numbers in terms of squares and dominos. For details, we refer to the excellent book of Benjamin and Quinn [5].

To provide combinatorial proofs of identities involving Leonardo p -numbers, we extend the arguments given in [13]. We define a new tile, called p -tile:

Definition 1. A p -tile is a rectangular tile defined as follows:

- It comes in one of p colors, which must occur as the initial piece in a tiling if it is included in the arrangement at all.
- It has a length l with $l \geq p + 1$, and is denoted by \mathcal{P}_l .

Let $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}$ denote the set of linear n -tilings using squares, p -minos, and p -tiles. For simplicity, we denote these members of $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}$ using sequences in \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{p} , and \mathcal{P}_l , respectively. For example, for $p = 3$ and $n = 4$, we have $\mathcal{K}_{3,4} = \{\mathbf{s}^4, \mathbf{p}, \mathcal{P}_4\}$. See Figure 1.

Figure 1: Tilings of length 4 for $p = 3$:

Since the \mathcal{P}_4 piece comes in one of 3 colors, we have

$$|\mathcal{K}_{3,4}| = 3 + 2 = 5 = \mathcal{L}_{3,4}.$$

For $p = 3, n = 5$, we have $\mathcal{K}_{3,5} = \{\mathbf{s}^5, \mathbf{sp}, \mathbf{ps}, \mathcal{P}_4\mathbf{s}, \mathcal{P}_5\}$. See Figure 2.

Figure 2: Tilings of length 5 for $p = 3$

Since \mathcal{P}_4 and \mathcal{P}_5 pieces come in one of 3 colors, we have

$$|\mathcal{K}_{3,5}| = 3 \cdot 2 + 3 = 9 = \mathcal{L}_{3,5}.$$

Proposition 1. *If $n \geq 0$, then $|\mathcal{K}_{p,n}| = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}$.*

Proof. Considering whether the final piece of $\lambda \in \mathcal{K}_{p,n}$, where $n \geq p + 1$, is **s** or **p** or if it equals \mathcal{P}_n (in which case, it consists of a single p -tile of length n), we get

$$|\mathcal{K}_{p,n}| = |\mathcal{K}_{p,n-1}| + |\mathcal{K}_{p,n-p-1}| + p.$$

Since p -tiles and p -minos have length greater than p , we have $|\mathcal{K}_{p,n}| = 1 = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}$ for $n = 0, 1, \dots, p$. □

Proposition 2. *For $n \geq 2p + 1$, we have*

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p} - \mathcal{L}_{p,n-2p-1},$$

with $\mathcal{L}_{p,0} = \mathcal{L}_{p,1} = \dots = \mathcal{L}_{p,p} = 1$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{p,p+1} &= \mathcal{L}_{p,p} + \mathcal{L}_{p,0} + p = 2 + p, \\ \mathcal{L}_{p,p+2} &= \mathcal{L}_{p,p+1} + \mathcal{L}_{p,1} + p = 3 + 2p, \\ \mathcal{L}_{p,p+3} &= \mathcal{L}_{p,p+2} + \mathcal{L}_{p,2} + p = 4 + 3p, \\ &\vdots \\ \mathcal{L}_{p,2p} &= \mathcal{L}_{p,2p-1} + \mathcal{L}_{p,p-1} + p = p^2 + p + 1. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The initial conditions follow from the definitions.

Suppose $n \geq 2p + 1$ and note that there are $\mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}$ members of $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}$ that ends in **s**.

Let S denote the subset of $\mathcal{K}_{p,n-p}$ consisting of those tilings that do not end in **p**. By subtraction, we have $|S| = \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p} - \mathcal{L}_{p,n-2p-1}$.

If $\lambda \in S$ ends in **s**, then let λ' be obtained from λ by replacing the final **s** with a **p**. Otherwise, $n \geq 2p + 1$ implies $\lambda = \mathcal{P}_{n-p}$ is also possible, where \mathcal{P}_{n-p} comes one of p colors. In this case, we let $\lambda' = \mathcal{P}_n$, keeping the color the same. Then

the mapping $\lambda \rightarrow \lambda'$ is a bijection from S to the subset of $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}$ whose members do not end in \mathbf{s} , and hence they number $\mathcal{L}_{p,n-p} - \mathcal{L}_{p,n-2p-1}$, which completes the proof. \square

For example, consider

$$\mathcal{K}_{3,7} = \{\mathbf{s}^7, \mathbf{ps}^3, \mathbf{sps}^2, \mathbf{s}^2\mathbf{ps}, \mathbf{s}^3\mathbf{p}, \mathcal{P}_4\mathbf{s}^3, \mathcal{P}_5\mathbf{s}^2, \mathcal{P}_6\mathbf{s}, \mathcal{P}_7\}.$$

There are $\mathcal{L}_{3,6} = 13$ members of $\mathcal{K}_{3,7}$ that end in \mathbf{s} . Now consider the subset S of $\mathcal{K}_{3,4} = \{\mathbf{s}^4, \mathbf{p}, \mathcal{P}_4\}$ that do not end in \mathbf{p} . So $S = \{\mathbf{s}^4, \mathcal{P}_4\}$. Since there is a bijection from S to the subset of $\mathcal{K}_{3,7}$ whose members do not end in \mathbf{s} , it is clear to see that $\mathbf{s}^4 \in S$ maps to $\mathbf{s}^3\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{K}_{3,7}$ and $\mathcal{P}_4 \in S$ maps to $\mathcal{P}_7 \in \mathcal{K}_{3,7}$. Thus

$$|\mathcal{K}_{3,7}| = |\mathcal{K}_{3,6}| + |S| = 13 + 4 = 17.$$

Proposition 3. For $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = (p + 1)F_{p,n+1} - p.$$

Proof. Let $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}^* := \mathcal{K}_{p,n} - \{\mathbf{s}^n\}$ denote the subset of tilings that do not contain only squares. There are $\mathcal{L}_{p,n} - 1$ tilings in $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}^*$. Now, $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}^*$ can be partitioned into two disjoint subsets, $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}^* = \mathcal{K}_{p,n}^{*1} \cup \mathcal{K}_{p,n}^{*2}$, where the set $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}^{*1}$ contains tilings with squares and at least one p -mino, and the set $\mathcal{K}_{p,n}^{*2}$ contains tilings with a p -tile, squares, and p -minos. Then, $|\mathcal{K}_{p,n}^{*1}| = F_{p,n+1} - 1$ and

$$|\mathcal{K}_{p,n}^{*2}| = p \sum_{l=p+1}^n F_{p,n+1-l} = p(F_{p,n+1} - 1).$$

Hence, $|\mathcal{K}_{p,n}^*| = (p + 1)(F_{p,n+1} - 1)$ which gives the desired result. \square

Proposition 4. For $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{p,i} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n+p+1} - (n + 1)p - 1.$$

Proof. Consider the $(n + p + 1)$ -tilings that do not contain any p -minos. Such tilings are either in the form of \mathbf{s}^{n+p+1} or $\mathcal{P}_l\mathbf{s}^{n+p+1-l}$ for $p + 1 \leq l \leq n + p + 1$, resulting in $p(n + 1) + 1$ such tilings. Since the number of $(n + p + 1)$ -tilings is $\mathcal{L}_{p,n+p+1}$, excluding those that do not contain any p -minos yields the right-hand side of the identity.

Let λ be a tiling of length $n + p + 1$ containing at least one p -mino. Conditioning on the position of the last p -mino, which covers cells $i + 1, \dots, i + p + 1$ ($0 \leq i \leq n$), such a tiling must have the form $\lambda = \lambda'\mathbf{ps}^{n-i}$ for ($1 \leq i \leq n$) where $\lambda' \in \mathcal{K}_{p,i}$, and there are $\mathcal{L}_{p,i}$ such tilings. Summing over i gives the left-hand side of the identity. \square

Next, we provide a combinatorial proof of the identity in [16, Theorem 2] for $m = 0$.

Proposition 5. *For $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)i} = \mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)n+1} - pn.$$

Proof. Consider the $(p + 1)n + 1$ -tilings that do not contain any squares. Such tilings are in the form of $\mathcal{P}_{(p+1)i+1} \mathbf{p}^{n-i}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$, resulting in pn such tilings. Since the number of $(p + 1)n + 1$ -tilings is $\mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)n+1}$, excluding those that do not contain any squares yields the right-hand side of the identity.

Let λ be a tiling of length $n + p + 1$ containing at least one square. Conditioning on the position of the last square, which covers cell $(p + 1)i$ where $(0 \leq i \leq n)$, such a tiling must have the form $\lambda = \lambda' s \mathbf{p}^{n-i}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$, where $\lambda' \in \mathcal{K}_{p,(p+1)i}$, and there are $\mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)i}$ such tilings. Summing over i gives the left-hand side of the identity. \square

Now, we provide a combinatorial interpretation of the incomplete Leonardo p -numbers $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k)$.

Let $\mathcal{A}_{p,n}$ denote the set consisting of tilings λ of length n such that the first piece of λ is assigned one of $p + 1$ colors provided λ is not all the square tiling, in which case the first piece of λ is not assigned a color. Then, from Proposition 3, we have

$$|\mathcal{A}_{p,n}| = (p + 1)(F_{p,n+1} - 1) + 1 = (p + 1)F_{p,n+1} - p = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}.$$

For $0 \leq k \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor$, let $\mathcal{A}_{p,n}(k)$ denote the subset of $\mathcal{A}_{p,n}$ containing at most k p -minos. Then

$$|\mathcal{A}_{p,n}(k)| = (p + 1) \sum_{i=0}^k \binom{n - pi}{i} - p. \tag{11}$$

Comparing (11) with (4), we get $|\mathcal{A}_{p,n}(k)| = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k)$.

It is clear to see that $|\mathcal{A}_{p,n}(\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor)| = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}$.

Proposition 6. *For $0 \leq k \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor$ and $n > p$, we have*

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k + 1) = \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}(k + 1) + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1}(k) + p.$$

Proof. Let $\lambda \in \mathcal{A}_{p,n}(k + 1)$, we condition on the last tile. If the last tile is square, there are $\mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}(k + 1)$ ways to tile the remaining $n - 1$ cells with at most $k + 1$ p -minos. If the last tile is p -mino, there are $\mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1}(k)$ ways to tile the first $n - p - 1$ cells with at most k p -minos. Note that the tiling of the form $s^{n-p-1} \mathbf{p}$ is counted without coloring. Hence, we must add p to account for these missed tilings. \square

Proposition 7. For $0 \leq k \leq \frac{n-p-r}{p+1}$, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^r \binom{r}{i} \mathcal{L}_{p,n+pi}(k+i) + (2^r - 1)p = \mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)r}(k+r).$$

Proof. Let $\lambda \in \mathcal{A}_{p,n+(p+1)r}(k+r)$ be a tiling of length $n + (p + 1)r$ containing at most $k + r$ p -minos. Suppose there are i p -minos among the last r tiles. Thus, λ is of the form $\lambda' \lambda''$ where $\lambda' \in \mathcal{A}_{p,n+p(r-i)}(k+r-i)$ and λ'' is a tiling with exactly i p -minos. There are $\binom{r}{i}$ ways to tiles λ'' and $\mathcal{L}_{p,n+pi}(k+i)$ possible ways to tiles λ' . Note that the tilings of the form $s^{n+p(r-i)} \lambda''$ are counted without coloring. Thus, we must multiply the number of such tilings by p , which gives us $p(2^r - 1)$. \square

Proposition 8. For $n \geq (p + 1)(k + 1)$, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p+i}(k) + rp = \mathcal{L}_{p,n+r}(k+1) - \mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k+1).$$

Proof. We will show that both sides of the identity count tilings of length $n + r$ with at most $k + 1$ p -minos such that the last p -mino from the right-hand side occupies position $(i + 1, \dots, i + p + 1)$ ($n - p \leq i \leq n + r - p - 1$). If there is a p -mino at position $(i + 1, \dots, i + p + 1)$ then there are $\mathcal{L}_{p,i}(k)$ ways to tile the first i cells. Note that when the first i cells are covered only with squares, the tiling is counted without coloring. There are r such tilings. \square

In [2], the authors define the hyper Leonardo p -numbers, $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k)}$, and provide the following explicit formula

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k)} = (p + 1) \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor} \binom{n+k-pi}{i+k} - p \binom{n+k}{k}. \tag{12}$$

Now, we give a combinatorial interpretation of hyper Leonardo p -numbers. Let $\mathcal{A}_{p,n}^{(k)}$ be the set of tilings λ of length $n + (p + 1)k$ that contain at least k p -minos, where the first tile of λ is assigned one of $p + 1$ colors, except when λ contains exactly k p -minos, in which case the first tile of λ is not assigned a color. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{A}_{p,n}^{(k)}| &= (p + 1) \sum_{i=k+1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor + k} \binom{n+(p+1)k-pi}{i} + \binom{n+(p+1)k-pk}{k} \\ &= (p + 1) \sum_{i=k}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor + k} \binom{n+k-p(i-k)}{i} - p \binom{n+k}{k} \\ &= (p + 1) \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor} \binom{n+k-pi}{i+k} - p \binom{n+k}{k} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k)}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 9. For $m, n \geq 1$ with $m \leq k$, we have

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n+m}^{(k)} = \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \mathcal{L}_{p,n+i}^{(k-i)}.$$

Proof. The left-hand side corresponds to the number of $(n + m + (p + 1)k)$ -tilings with at least k p -minos. There are $\binom{m}{i}$ ways to select the positions of i p -minos that appear among the first m tiles. The number of ways to tile the remaining $n + p(k - i) + k$ -tilings with at least $k - i$ p -minos is $\mathcal{L}_{p,n+i}^{(k-i)}$. Summing over all values of i yields the right-hand side of the identity. \square

Next, we provide tiling proofs of the following two recurrences relations from [2].

Proposition 10. For $n, k \geq 1$, we have

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k)} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}^{(k)} + \mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k-1)}.$$

with $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(0)} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{p,0}^{(k)} = \mathcal{L}_{p,0}$.

Proof. Let $\lambda \in \mathcal{A}_{p,n}^{(k)}$ be a $n + (p + 1)k$ -tiling with at least k p -minos. For $k = 0$, we get $|\mathcal{A}_{p,n}^{(0)}| = |\mathcal{A}_{p,n}| = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}$, and for $n = 0$, we obtain $|\mathcal{A}_{p,0}^{(k)}| = 1 = \mathcal{L}_{p,0}$. Now, assuming $n, k \geq 1$, if the last tile of λ is a square, then there are $\mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}^{(k)}$ ways to tile the remaining $n - 1 + (p + 1)k$ -tiling with at least k p -minos. Otherwise, if the last tile is a p -mino, then there are $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k-1)}$ ways to tile the remaining $n + (p + 1)(k - 1)$ -tilings with at least $k - 1$ p -minos. Considering both cases, we obtain the desired result. \square

Proposition 11. For $n > p$ and $k \geq 1$, we have

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)k} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)k}(k - 1) + \mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k)} + p \binom{n + k}{k}.$$

Proof. For $0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor + k$, let $\mathcal{A}_{p,n+(p+1)k,i} \in \mathcal{A}_{p,n+(p+1)k}$ be the subset of $n + (p + 1)k$ -tilings using exactly i p -minos. It is clear that

$$\mathcal{A}_{p,n+(p+1)k} = \bigcup_i \mathcal{A}_{p,n+(p+1)k,i}.$$

Using combinatorial interpretation of incomplete Leonardo p -numbers we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^{k-1} |\mathcal{A}_{p,n+(p+1)k,i}| = \mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)k}(k - 1). \tag{13}$$

Note that the first piece in the tilings of $\mathcal{A}_{p,n+(p+1)k,k}$ is assigned $p+1$ colors. Then, from the combinatorial interpretation of hyper Leonardo numbers, we obtain

$$\sum_{i=k}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor + k} |\mathcal{A}_{p,n+(p+1)k,i}| = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k)} + p \binom{n+k}{k}. \tag{14}$$

Combining (13) and (14), we obtain the desired result. □

3. Combinatorial Interpretation of Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers

In this section, we give a combinatorial interpretation of the Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers. We provide combinatorial proofs of the identities (6)-(10). We also introduce the hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers, which is a new family of sequences in OEIS [10].

Recall that a *circular n -board* is obtained from an n -board by attaching the right side of the n th cell to the left side of the first cell. A bracelet length n (or *n -bracelet*) is a tiling of a circular n -board. Here, the cells and tiles are labeled in a clockwise direction, with the first tile designated as the one that covers cell 1.

Let $l_{p,n}$ denote the set of n -bracelets that can be made using curved squares and p -minos. A bracelet is said to have phase r (or *r -phase*) where $1 \leq r \leq p+1$ if the r th cell of the first tile covers cell 1. We denote by \mathbf{p}_r a curved p -mino whose r th cell covers cell 1. Then, since there is only one way to tile a circular n -board using only squares, we have $|l_{p,n}| = 1$ for $1 \leq n \leq p$. Since a circular $(p+1)$ -board can be tiled with squares or with one p -mino arranged in $p+1$ different phases, we have $|l_{p,p+1}| = p+2$ for $n = p+1$. We define $|l_{p,0}| = p+1$ and interpret this as the number of phases. For $n \geq p+1$, considering whether the last tile, the one that precedes the first tile, of the n -bracelet is square or p -mino implies $|l_{p,n}| = |l_{p,n-1}| + |l_{p,n-p-1}|$. Thus, we have

$$|l_{p,n}| = L_{p,n}$$

for $n \geq 0$. That is, the Lucas p -numbers count the number of ways to tile a circular n -board using curved squares and p -minos. Note that for $p = 1$, it reduces to the combinatorial interpretation of classical Lucas numbers. For details, we refer to [5].

In the Figure 3, we illustrate all 4-bracelets that can be made using curved squares and 2-minos $\{\mathbf{p}_1s, s\mathbf{p}, s^4, \mathbf{p}_2s, \mathbf{p}_3s\}$.

Now, we provide a combinatorial interpretation of Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers. Throughout this section, we consider all tiles as curved tiles. We define a (curved) p -tile as follows:

- A p -tile is a circular piece with length $l \geq p+1$ coming in one of p colors, which must occur as the first tile in an n -bracelet if it is included in the arrangement at all.

Figure 3: All 4-bracelets that can be made using squares and 2-minos

- If the p -tile has length $p + 1$, then it can be in $p + 1$ phases. We denote by \mathcal{P}_{p+1}^r a p -tile whose r th cell covers cell 1 of the bracelet. Otherwise, the p -tile of length l with $l > p + 1$, denoted by \mathcal{P}_l , must start from cell 1.

Let $\mathcal{B}_{p,n}$ denote the set of n -bracelets that can be made using curved squares, p -minos, and p -tiles. In Figure 4, we illustrate 13 possible bracelets for $n = 4, p = 2$. The p -tiles \mathcal{P}_3^r ($1 \leq r \leq 3$) and \mathcal{P}_4 come in one of 2 possible colors.

$$\mathcal{B}_{2,4} = \{\mathbf{p}_1s, s\mathbf{p}, s^4, \mathbf{p}_2s, \mathbf{p}_3s, \mathcal{P}_3^1s, \mathcal{P}_3^2s, \mathcal{P}_3^3s, \mathcal{P}_4\}$$

Figure 4: All 4-bracelets that can be made using squares and 2-minos

Proposition 12. For $n \geq 0$, we have $|\mathcal{B}_{p,n}| = \mathcal{R}_{p,n}$.

Proof. Considering whether the final piece of $\lambda \in \mathcal{B}_{p,n}$ where $n \geq p + 1$ is \mathbf{s} or \mathbf{p} or if it equals \mathcal{P}_n (in which case, it consists of a single p -tile of length n), we get

$$|\mathcal{B}_{p,n}| = |\mathcal{B}_{p,n-1}| + |\mathcal{B}_{p,n-p-1}| + p.$$

Since p -tiles and p -minos have length greater than p , we have $|\mathcal{B}_{p,n}| = 1 = \mathcal{R}_{p,n}$ for $n = 1, \dots, p$, and $|\mathcal{B}_{p,0}| = p^2 + p + 1 = \mathcal{R}_{p,0}$, where $p + 1$ corresponds to the number

of phases of a p -mino, and p^2 is the number of colored phases of a p -tile excluding phase 1. \square

Proposition 13. *For $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n} = (p + 1)L_{p,n} - p.$$

Proof. Let $\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^* := \mathcal{B}_{p,n} - \{s^n\}$ denote the subset of n -bracelets without only squares. There are $\mathcal{R}_{p,n} - 1$ bracelets in $\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^*$. Now, $\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^*$ can be partitioned into two disjoint subsets, $\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^* = \mathcal{B}_{p,n}^{*1} \cup \mathcal{B}_{p,n}^{*2}$, where $\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^{*1}$ contains n -bracelets with squares and at least one p -mino, and where $\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^{*2}$ contains n -bracelets with p -tiles, squares, and p -minos. Then, we have $|\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^{*1}| = L_{p,n} - 1$. To count the number of bracelets in $\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^{*2}$, we consider the following two cases.

If the p -tile has length $p + 1$, then there are $p + 1$ different phases to arrange it, each in one of the p colors. The number of ways to tile the remaining $n - p - 1$ cells is given by $F_{p,n-p}$. Then, $|\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^{*2}| = p(p + 1)F_{p,n-p}$.

If the p -tile has length $l \geq p + 2$, the number of ways to tile the remaining $n - p - 2$ cells is

$$\sum_{j=0}^{n-p-2} F_{p,j+1} = F_{p,n+1} - F_{p,n-p} - 1.$$

Thus, we have

$$|\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^{*2}| = p(p + 1)F_{p,n-p} + p(F_{p,n+1} - F_{p,n-p} - 1) = p(L_{p,n} - 1).$$

Hence, $|\mathcal{B}_{p,n}^*| = (p + 1)L_{p,n} - p - 1$ which gives the desired result. \square

Proposition 14. *For $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n} = (p + 1)\mathcal{L}_{p,n} - p\mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}.$$

Proof. Let λ be an n -bracelet. There are two cases to consider.

If λ is breakable at cell n (i.e., the first tile starts at cell 1), then λ can be converted into a linear tiling, and there are $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}$ such tilings.

If λ is unbreakable at cell n , then the first tile is either a p -mino or a p -tile of length $p + 1$ at phase r ($2 \leq r \leq p + 1$). If the first tile is a p -mino, then there are p ways to arrange it, and $F_{p,n-p}$ ways to tile the remaining cells. If the first tile is a p -tile of length $p + 1$, then there are p ways to arrange it, each in one of the p colors, and $F_{p,n-p}$ ways to tile the remaining cells. So, we have

$$p(pF_{p,n-p} + F_{p,n-p}) = p(\mathcal{L}_{p,n} - \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}).$$

Considering both cases, we obtain the desired results. \square

Proposition 15. For $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \mathcal{R}_{p,i} = \mathcal{R}_{p,n+p+1} - p(n+1) - 1. \tag{15}$$

Proof. Consider the $(n + p + 1)$ -bracelets that do not contain any p -minos. Such tilings are either in the form of s^{n+p+1} or $\mathcal{P}_{p+1}^1 s^n, \mathcal{P}_l s^{n+p+1-l}$ for $p+2 \leq l \leq n+p+1$, resulting in $p(n+1) + 1$ such bracelets. Since the number of $(n + p + 1)$ -bracelets is $\mathcal{R}_{p,n+p+1}$, excluding those that do not contain any p -minos yields the right-hand side of the identity.

The remaining bracelets must have at least one p -mino and have one of the following forms:

1. $\mathcal{P}_{p+1}^r s^n$ for $2 \leq r \leq p+1$,
2. $\mathbf{p}^r s^n$ for $1 \leq r \leq p+1$,
3. $\lambda' \mathbf{p} s^{n-i}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$, where $\lambda' \in \mathcal{B}_{p,i}$.

There are p^2 bracelets of the first form and $p+1$ bracelets of the second form, giving a total of $p^2 + p + 1 = \mathcal{R}_{p,0}$. For the third type of bracelets, we condition on the position of the last p -mino, which covers cells $i+1, \dots, i+p+1$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. These bracelets can be transformed into i -bracelets by removing the pieces $\mathbf{p} s^{n-i}$. Gluing the remaining pieces together results in $\mathcal{R}_{p,i}$ such bracelets (see Figure 5). Summing over i gives $\sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{R}_{p,i}$. Combining these three cases, we obtain the left-hand side of the identity. \square

Figure 5: Transforming a bracelet in the form of $\lambda' \mathbf{p} s^{n-i}$ to λ'

Proposition 16. For $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \mathcal{R}_{p,(p+1)i} = \mathcal{R}_{p,(p+1)n+1} - p(n-p-1). \tag{16}$$

Proof. The proof of the identity (16) is similar to that of Proposition 5, considering the position of the last square within $((p + 1)n + 1)$ -bracelets. \square

Now, we give a combinatorial interpretation of incomplete Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers.

Let $\mathcal{C}_{p,n}$ denote the set consisting of n -bracelets λ . The first piece of λ is assigned one of $p + 1$ colors, provided λ is not the entire square bracelet. If λ is the entire square bracelet, then the first piece of λ is not assigned a color. Then, from the proof of relation (6), we have

$$|\mathcal{C}_{p,n}| = (p + 1)(L_{p,n} - 1) + 1 = (p + 1)L_{p,n} - p = \mathcal{R}_{p,n}.$$

For $0 \leq k \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor$, let $\mathcal{C}_{p,n}(k)$ denote the subset of $\mathcal{C}_{p,n}$ containing at most k p -minos. It is well known that $L_{p,n} = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor} \frac{n}{n-pi} \binom{n-pi}{i}$, then

$$|\mathcal{C}_{p,n}(k)| = (p + 1) \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{n}{n-pi} \binom{n-pi}{i} - p. \tag{17}$$

Comparing (17) with (8), we get $|\mathcal{C}_{p,n}(k)| = \mathcal{R}_{p,n}(k)$.

Proposition 17. For $0 \leq k \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor$ and $n > p$, we have

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n}(k + 1) = \mathcal{R}_{p,n-1}(k + 1) + \mathcal{R}_{p,n-p-1}(k) + p.$$

Proof. We condition on the last tile. If the last tile is square, there are $\mathcal{R}_{p,n-1}(k + 1)$ ways to tile the remaining $n - 1$ cells with at most $k + 1$ p -minos. If the last tile is a p -mino, there are $\mathcal{R}_{p,n-p-1}(k)$ ways to tile the first $n - p - 1$ cells with at most k p -minos. Note that the tiling of the form $s^{n-p-1}\mathbf{p}$ is counted without coloring. Hence, we must add p to account for these missed tilings. \square

Proposition 18. For $0 \leq n \leq \frac{n-p-r}{p+1}$, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^r \binom{r}{i} \mathcal{R}_{p,n+pi}(k + i) + (2^r - 1)p = \mathcal{R}_{p,n+(p+1)r}(k + r). \tag{18}$$

Proof. The proof is similar to the Proposition 7. \square

Now we establish a link between incomplete Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers and Leonardo p -numbers. To do this, we introduce the concept of hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers.

The hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -number $\mathcal{R}_{p,n}^{(k)}$ counts the number of circular tilings of length $n + (p + 1)k$ with at least k p -minos. Such a tiling λ , the first tile is assigned one of $p + 1$ colors, except when λ has phase 1 bracelet with exactly k p -minos. In this case, the first tile of λ is not assigned a color. Thus, we give the following definition.

Definition 2. For $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 1$, the hyper Lucas-leonardo p -numbers are defined by

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n}^{(k)} = (p + 1) \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \rfloor} \frac{n + (p + 1)k}{n + k - pi} \binom{n + k - pi}{i + k} - p \binom{n + k}{k},$$

with $\mathcal{R}_{p,n}^{(0)} = \mathcal{R}_{p,n}$, $\mathcal{R}_{p,0}^{(k)} = \mathcal{R}_{p,0} = p^2 + p + 1$.

Some special cases for the hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -sequence can be given as follows. For $p = 1$, we get the hyper Lucas-Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{R}_n^{(k)}\}$. In particular, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \{\mathcal{R}_n^{(1)}\} &= \{3, 4, 9, 16, 29, 50, 85, 122, \dots\}, \\ \{\mathcal{R}_n^{(2)}\} &= \{3, 7, 16, 32, 61, 101, 186, 308, \dots\}, \\ \{\mathcal{R}_n^{(3)}\} &= \{3, 10, 26, 58, 119, 220, 406, 714, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

For $p = 2$, we get the hyper Lucas-Leonardo 2-sequence. In particular, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \{\mathcal{R}_{2,n}^{(1)}\} &= \{7, 8, 9, 19, 32, 48, 76, 119, 180, \dots\}, \\ \{\mathcal{R}_{2,n}^{(2)}\} &= \{7, 15, 24, 43, 75, 123, 199, 318, 498, \dots\}, \\ \{\mathcal{R}_{2,n}^{(3)}\} &= \{7, 22, 46, 89, 164, 287, 486, 804, 1302, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

We note that for $p > 1$, we observe that the hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -sequences are new additions in OEIS [10].

Proposition 19. For $n > p \geq 1$ and $k \geq 1$, we have

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n}^{(k)} = \mathcal{R}_{p,n+(p+1)k} - \mathcal{R}_{p,n+(p+1)k}(k - 1) - p \binom{n + k}{k}.$$

Proof. By using Definition 2 and relation (9), we get the desired result. □

Finally, we give a relationship between hyper Leonardo p -numbers and hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers.

Proposition 20. For $n > p \geq 1$ and $k \geq 1$, we have

$$\mathcal{R}_{p,n}^{(k)} = (p + 1)\mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k)} - p\mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}^{(k)} + p^2 \binom{n + k - 1}{k}.$$

Proof. From Proposition 11 and using the relations (7) and (10), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 (p+1)\mathcal{L}_{p,n}^{(k)} - p\mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}^{(k)} &= ((p+1)\mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)k} - p\mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)k-1}) \\
 &\quad - ((p+1)\mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)k}(k-1) - p\mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)k-1}(k-1)) \\
 &\quad - (p^2+p)\binom{n+k}{k} + p^2\binom{n+k-1}{k} \\
 &= \mathcal{R}_{p,n+(p+1)k} - \mathcal{R}_{p,n+(p+1)k}(k-1) - p^2\binom{n+k-1}{k-1} \\
 &\quad - p\binom{n+k}{k}.
 \end{aligned}$$

By using Proposition 19, we get the desired result. □

4. Concluding Remarks

This paper provides combinatorial interpretations of Leonardo p -numbers and Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers while also extending the incomplete and hyper analogs. Our results offer combinatorial interpretations and reveal several new identities related to hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers. In future work, we plan to investigate additional identities and properties of hyper Lucas-Leonardo p -numbers.

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